
Grid Connected to Renewable Energy Resources

Srikanth¹ and Hima Bindu²

Department of Electrical and Electronics Engineering, KL University, Vijayawada, AP, India
Corresponding Author: kssrikanth189@gmail.com

To Cite this Article

Srikanth and Hima Bindu, "Grid Connected to Renewable Energy Resources", Journal of Engineering Technology and Sciences, Vol. 01, Issue 04, December 2024, pp:18-22

Abstract: Grid connected renewable energy systems integrate such renewable energy sources as solar, wind, hydro and biomass into current power networks. These systems are critical to generating sustainable energy behaviors and reducing reliance on fossil fuels. By being connected to the grid, renewable energy facilities ensure a steady, reliable supply of energy, because they can draw power from the grid when their generation is low, and deliver excess electricity when it's high. Solar photovoltaic (PV) systems and wind turbines are the two most common renewable energy sources that are tied into the grid. The kinetic energy from wind is captured by wind turbines, the kinetic energy of sunlight is converted to electricity by solar photovoltaic systems. Both systems feed electricity directly into the grid through inverters which convert DC power to AC at grid frequency and voltage. There are a number of advantages associated with having systems that are in communication with the grid. First, they help provide energy security, stabilize energy prices and reduce greenhouse gas emissions. In addition, excess energy generated by these systems can be exchanged to the grid under feed-in tariff or net metering schemes through which those who are 'producing' credits or revenue.

Keywords: PV panels, Fuel cells, Hydrogen, Grid, Windmill

I. Introduction

Because the world is still in the Industrialization waves, increasing population, and improving technology, the world's energy demand is still on the rise. But conventional energy sources, including fossil fuels, have a leading role in climate change, greenhouse gas emissions, and environmental decline. These issues have led to renewable energy sources as an important part of viable sustainable energy solutions. Grid-connected renewable energy systems, including solar, wind, hydro, geothermal, biomass, are playing an increasingly important role in changing the global energy landscape.

A grid connected renewable energy system consists of connecting renewable energy producing units to the central power grid and electricity can flow in both respects. These devices enable renewable energy providers to pull power when renewable generation is not enough (like during low sun or wind), and to provide excess electricity onto the grid. By combining with a smooth and dependable supply of energy, this integration resolves the intermittent problem facing renewable resources.

II. Overview of Renewable Energy Resources to Grid

There are two well-known renewable energy sources, wind and solar energy. Solar photovoltaic (PV) systems, however, capture the energy of the sun, while wind turbines harness the kinetic energy of the wind. Both technologies require inverters to change generated direct current (DC) electricity into grid compatible alternating current (AC). Hydropower is another important renewable energy source in the sense that it produces electricity by the use of flowing water and it provides a steady and reliable energy supply. Biomass energy is where we turn it into heat or electricity, but geothermal systems are devices that get the heat from under the surface of the Earth.

Many of the reasons to integrate renewable energy into the grid are social, economic or environmental. It reduces greenhouse gas emissions dramatically, so lessening the impacts of climate change. However renewable energy decreases reliance on finite fossil fuel supplies, stabilizes energy prices over time and improves energy security. Typically, the systems are grid connected and allow for the consumer to add energy to the grid through feed in tariffs or net metering and pay per kilowatt hour a retail price.

(a) Without battery back-up

(b) With battery storage

Fig 1: Grid connected to PV Panels

Although renewable energy has benefits, integration into the grid is very difficult. Wind and solar energy are sporadic and can cause power supply fluctuations leading to grid stability issues. These swings need to be mitigated by advanced energy storage devices, such as batteries, and by the deployment of smart grid technologies that optimize energy distribution and use. Additionally, renewable energy systems might have high upfront costs, but once established, there are also long term savings, as well as underlying government subsidies.

As the environmental concerns and technological advances bring more and more awareness on renewable energy systems all over the globe, grid connected renewable energy systems have become more and more popular. Realising that the only way we can meet global sustainability is through clean energy, communities and nations are now switching to clean sources of energy. Integrating a variety of renewable energy sources into a power grid not only promotes good stewardship of the environment but also good economy and energy resiliency. In brief, the widespread use of grid connected renewable energy sources can provide a truly sustainable way of getting our energy. These systems deliver a cleaner, greener and more resilient energy future by exploiting the full potential of potentially diverse renewable sources, and combining it with the existing energy infrastructure.

III. Renewable Energy Resources connected to On-Grid and Off-Grid

The two main categories of renewable energy systems are on grid and off grid, which are built to cater to specific energy requirements and to specific infrastructure conditions. Both strategies rely on renewable energies, such as solar, wind, hydro and biomass, to produce sustainable electricity, but their method, connectivity and applications are very different.

Fig 2: On-Grid mode

On grid, or grid tied systems, are deployment of systems which are directly connected to the main electrical grid. A smooth and dependable energy supply is guaranteed by these systems allowing energy producers the capacity to trade electricity into the grid. On grid systems are largely used in commercial, industrial, and residential contexts when grid connectivity is available. Two-Way Power Flow: In addition, on grid systems can return extra electricity produced by renewable energy sources such as solar panels and wind turbines to the grid. The system runs on grid electricity, which is used when the output of renewable energy is not enough. Many on grid systems come with a net metering feature which monitors the importation and exportation of electricity from the grid. This arrangement may have financial advantages because consumers get credit for excess energy they return to the grid. On grid systems are not deprived of backup storage because the grid acts as an energy reservoir, so the initial setup cost is much lower. Dependency on Grid Availability: The main drawback of on grid solutions is the reliance on the grid. Most on grid systems turn off to protect utility workers during power outages unless they have such extra parts as batteries and islanding inverters. For locations with reliable grid infrastructure, on-grid systems provide a cost-effective means of integrating renewable energy into current electricity networks.

Off grid systems work independently of the national electric grid. These are power providing systems, designed for isolated or undeveloped locations experiencing unpredictable or nonexistent grid utility. Renewable energy off-grid systems only rely locally produced renewable energy with or without energy storage devices to supply electricity.

Fig 3: Off-Grid connected to PV Panels

Stand alone or off grid systems are self-contained or independent of source other than that which is provided by the system itself. Because they are particularly useful in rural, isolated or disaster-prone areas. However, off grid systems are usually combined with batteries or other storage technologies as buffers of excess energy, to supply energy where there is inadequate generation. The use of backup generators and energy storage may add added expense to off grid system design. However, they offer long term savings with respect to dependence on grid power. For specific energy demands, off grid systems are specific to location, resources available and load requirements. Off grid solutions are applicable on applications where grid extension is not possible, like in the case of isolated towns, houses or industrial sites far from existing infrastructure.

IV. Applications of On-Grid Off-Grid and Hybrid Systems

On-Grid Renewable Energy System Applications: Solar photovoltaic (PV) systems are installed on grid sometimes in residence to reduce electricity costs and carbon emissions. Net metering allows homeowners to sell excess energy back to the grid and become financially motivated to make that happen. Large scale installations in factories and warehouse or commercial building for cost reduction and improved efficiency of energy. Wind and solar farms supply electricity to the grid, and satisfy large scale energy demands. Renewable energy technologies power transportation systems, public buildings, and streetlights. Grid connected solutions mitigate the disadvantages of high energy needs in cities with high energy usage. On grid systems use peer to peer (P2P) or energy markets to facilitate energy trade through the use of blockchain technology for efficiency and transparency. On grid renewable energy systems are fed into smart networks in order to optimise energy generation, storage and distribution. These systems improve grid stability.

Utilising Renewable Energy Off-Grid Systems: Off grid systems are the turnkey solution for powering isolated communities, islands and mountainous areas, where grid extension is no longer an option. These systems supply the necessary energy to cook, light and power this and other appliances. The practices move towards sustainable farming through wind powered irrigation systems and off grid solar water pumps. These devices reduce dependence on diesel powered pumps, which helps save the farmers from spending money on their operating expenses. Off grid renewable energy systems are also used in the disaster affected areas to provide temporary electricity for emergency electricity to temporary shelters, medical facilities and communication networks. Off grid systems are used to power remote telecommunication towers and monitoring stations used in wildlife conservation or mining, and in weather forecasting. These small off grid systems provide electricity for cooking, lighting and charging for cabins, RVing and campgrounds. Off grid renewable solutions provide electricity to distant military installations and operations, reducing dependency on traditional fuel.

Hybrid Systems: During blackouts, hybrid systems make sure of a continuous supply of electricity by alternating between local renewable energy sources and grid power. Microgrids powered by a combination of off grid and on grid mechanics, can localise campus power or power a small community. The Hybrid Battery Storage system companies use with them to keep operating in the event of a grid outage.

V. Conclusion

There are a number of uses for rights systems linked to renewable energy sources which are off or on the grid. Such systems present a clean, dependable and reasonable priced energy solutions tailored to individual needs, from illuminating rural locations to aiding in emergency operations. Their much versatility is ensuring a guaranteed sustainable future for every industry.

References

- [1] M. Singh Sharma, M. Singh Khan, and P. Raghavendra Rao 2004, "Islanding Grid vs Standalone Grid using PV Panels." In Proceedings of the 7th Annual Springer international Conference on Grid Systems (Bombay, India, May 12-32, 2010).
- [2] K V Rao Patel and A. Naga Jyothi, "Power Consumption in Grid Monitoring in Standalone Systems" Wireless Satellite Communications, IEEE Volume 01, Issue 03, April. 2012 Page(s):56-62
- [3] P. Rajendra Singh, S. Anand Mehata, M. Tole Whang Sukhe, "Power Transmission in Grid using Grid System" Mc Graw Hill Press 2001, Chapter 14, Page(s): 23-122
- [4] N.Rana Pratap Singh and J.K. Tony Jaa, "Distribution of Power in Different Sectors using SCADA in Wireless Networks using Relays Concepts: Open Discussions in Relay Networks," IEEE Volume 07, Issue 05, March. 2014 Page(s):87-98
- [5] M. Lohit Khan, S. Manoj Yadav and E.Rohit Kapoor Sivakumar, "Implementation of Grid Technology in Communication Systems Networks" Workshop on Grid Technology, 2012. Proceedings. Conference on 12-13 December. 2010 Page(s):12-21
- [6] C K.Sohail Mehata Khan, P.S.Arbaz Singh and Sk.Islam Khan, "Wireless Relay Networks in MIMO Designing Concepts using Grid Technology throughput enhancement in wireless networks" Areas in Wireless Communications, IEEE Journal on Volume 10, Issue 6, December 2012 Page(s):61 – 72

- [7] D. Ajay Kumar, A. Rahul Pratap Singh and N.Mohit Singh, "Satellite Relay Networks in MIMO Technology in PV Grid Systems" Springer 2014. Proceedings Volume 7, 11-14 October. 2010 Page(s):118-121